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Title:

**Human capital for Tourism industry
Evidence from Algeria**

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Human capital for Tourism industry Evidence from Algeria

Abstract:

Nowadays, the human capital is the essence of the growth of the economies because it is the engine of every industry and firm. Product or service, the human is the most important ring in the process of production. Tourism appears in the latest decades as the most important factor for the economic growth due to its green benefits. Algeria due to its treasure of touristic places must give the great intention to this sector especially after the fall of hydrocarbon prices. Therefore, investing in the human capital through the training in Algeria for the tourism sector will be the appropriate solution for Algeria to survive due to sustainability of tourism sector.

Key words: tourism, human capital, training, Algeria.

Jel code: L83, J24, O15, M53,

ملخص:

في الوقت الحاضر، رأس المال البشري هو جوهر نمو الاقتصادات لأنه هو محرك كل صناعة أو الشركة. سواء كان المنتج سلع أو خدمة، الإنسان هو أهم حلقة في عملية الإنتاج. يبدو السياحة في العقود الأخيرة على أنها العامل الأكثر أهمية بالنسبة للنمو الاقتصادي نظرا لفوائدها الخالية من النفايات. الجزائر بسبب كنزها من الأماكن السياحية يجب أن تعطي أهمية كبيرة لهذا القطاع خاصة بعد انخفاض أسعار النفط والغاز. وبالتالي، فإن الاستثمار في رأس المال البشري من خلال التدريب في الجزائر لقطاع السياحة سيكون الحل المناسب للجزائر من أجل البقاء بفضل استدامة قطاع السياحة.

الكلمات المفتاحية: السياحة، رأس المال البشري، التدريب، الجزائر

Introduction:

Following the deterioration in the oil prices ([Aasim M. Husain et al. 2015](#)), the economies based on hydrocarbon are obliged to look for other sources to generate more incomes and to hire more employees. These sources are characterized in alternative sectors such as agriculture, industry out of hydrocarbons, services ...etc. Following the report of ([Eichengreen and Gupta 2011](#)), the first sector that it boost India to grow is the services sector due to the rapid growth from a side, and the direct contribution in the economic development , generating revenues and creating employment. Following the WTO, Tourism and travel-related services are services provided by hotels and restaurants (including catering), travel agencies and tour operator services, tourist guide services and other related services.

According to Guillermo Valles⁴,The oceans and seas play a major role in helping to achieve sustainable development, economic growth and improved livelihoods for people ([Guillermo Valles 2016](#)). Also, half of the worlds tourists choose to spend their time in coastal areas. According to the latest statistics of WTTC ([WTTC 2016c](#)), WTTC is forecasting a bit of a boom for 2015 in the west African country of the Gambia. It's predicted to have the strongest growth of all 184 countries WTTC researches in terms of its contribution from travel & tourism to GDP, employment and money received from international visitors. This year, GDP from Tourism to the Gambia will grow by 15.8% where China in the tenth place from GDP growth that it increases a respectable 7.5%.

The tourism has seen a big interest from the researchers in the latest years according to its direct effect in the economic growth of economics did not have just their strategic place to exploit it and transfer it to the first source to grow with the economy as Tunisia and Morocco.

According to ([UNCTAD secretariat 2010, 1](#)), the tourism is not emerged just as a driver for economic progress, but also for social development.

According to the study of ([Jaziri and Boussaffa 2010](#)), “Tourism today is a mean of the protection and enhancement of natural sites with tourism potential, promotion of local culture and heritage and reduction of poverty”.

Following the data of ([IATA 2016](#)), Over 200 million people work in the travel and tourism industry worldwide the matter that sow the necessity of the human capital in the tourism.

⁴ Mr. Guillermo Valles, Director, Division on international Trade in Goods and Services, and Commodities (DITC), UNCTAD

There for, we will start in this paper with some literature review about the tourism and tourism industry and the importance of tourism as an important factor for the economic growth. In the second part, we demonstrate the tourism industry in general. In the next part, we move to mention the importance of the human capital and training in tourism sector. In the section after, quick view of tourism in some selected countries with a clear description of the tourism sector in Algeria. In the end, conclusion and some recommendations for the importance of the training in the tourism sector.

Literature revue:

There are many studies turn around the tourism industry, tourism effect on economic growth. These are some of the latest results on the tourism research.

Li, Huang, and Song 2017:

Following the study of (Li, Huang, and Song 2016, 2), “compared to manufacturing and energy industries, tourism is an experience based industry and has distinctive features of industry operation”.

Zhang and Gao 2016:

There are different studies about the tourism effect on economic growth. According to (Zhang and Gao 2016), the tourism has a positive effect on economic growth and CO2 in the long run.

Tetzschner and Herlau 2003:

In the first side of the study of (Tetzschner and Herlau 2003), the tourist industry has come to be recognized from the past as an important way of providing strategic supports for sustainable local business development. Where in the second one, the connection between the entrepreneurship and innovation and tourism has a great effect in the economy following their direct effect in the economy. From the important results gathered is the necessity of creating the social entrepreneurship in the society to promote the local business development.

According to (Ashley 2009), “the tourism is one of the important economic growth in Africa due to their geographic places”

Rogerson 2001:

If we tried to define the tourism, Following the study of (Rogerson 2001), “there are different government insert the tourism as one of the important strategies for the growth of the state”.

If we tried to look for the tourist service, it is not tourist product in its own characteristics but it must be correlated with another product or another sector

According to world travel and tourism council (Rogerson 2001, 124),”the tourism is both the world’s fastest growing industry and the world’s largest source of job opportunities”.

However, following (Roberto Crotti and Tiffany Misrahi 2015, 44), the Algeria rank in the place 138 in the field of the tourist service infrastructure.

Agaraj and Murati 2009:

Following the research of (Agaraj and Murati 2009), tourism has become an important sector that has an impact on development of country economy. The main benefits of tourism are income creation and generation of jobs. For many regions and countries, it is the most important source of welfare. The ability of the national economy to benefit from tourism depends on the availability of investment to develop the necessary infrastructure and on its ability to supply the needs of tourists.

Tourism industry:

In today's world, tourism is widely recognized by various business houses, international funding agencies, as well as various governments as an effective way to raise the development of the economy of a country; so much so that emerging economies like India have begun to consider it an alternative source of economic growth (Oppermann and Chon 1997; Sindiga 1999).

In addition, following the technologic advancement and the improvement in communication, tourism has become one of the fastest growing industries now days, where the global tourism is expected to continue to expand because people are beginning to discover more and more new destination and the travel industry is becoming more and more organized (Mowforth and Munt 1997, 17)

The tourism hotel industry has shown a steady growth with a rate of approximately 14% during last few years. From this point, we can guess that it plays an important role in the economic growth, where we find that different government launched dispositive to enhance the tourism to getting so goals such as(Dhar 2015):

- Generate employment opportunities,
- Infrastructure development,
- Financial benefits for external change.

In addition to the previous results, we can have said also that tourism is the source of different benefits such as:

- technology and knowledge spillover,
- tourism from the important sector generating the hard currency (safe-haven currency)
- tourism is the industry of the present and the future because its products do not relate with time, and it does not generate wastes

The tourism industry affects the other sectors by the spillover effect. According to the study of (Zhang and Gao 2016, 226), the tourism industry may stimulate the economic growth by generating positive externalities in non-tourism sectors such as manufacturing industry, transportation industry and service industry. In addition, tourism development brings about a number of benefits such as revenue income, job chance and improvement of image.

In addition to the positive effects of tourism, there is also the negative side of the tourism where the tourism boom affects in bad way such as:

- different environmental pressure;
- increasing noise;
- increasing biodiversity loss;
- increasing the CO2 emission;
- etc. ...

Tourism contributes more than 9% to the world's GDP and one out of every 11 jobs, and is growing faster than other segments of the global economy. Read our report on how a "smart travel" model could fire up growth and job creation in the industry. What does the smart travelling mean to you?⁵

The effect of the tourism in the economy:

According to (UNCTAD secretariat 2010), the tourism affect different sectors:

- Reduce poverty, following the study of (Blake et al. 2008), the tourism is considered as one of the important policies for the economic development where it is a revenue generator for poor families in brazil.
- Empower women, youth and migrant workers with new employment opportunities

⁵ http://www.weforum.org/reports/smart-travel-unlocking-economic-growth-and-development-through-travelfacilitation?utm_content=buffer44232&utm_medium=social&utm_source=facebook.com&utm_campaign=buffer

- Revive declining urban areas,
- Open up and develop remote rural areas,
- Promote the conservation of countries environmental endowments and cultural heritages.

The importance of human capital and training in tourism:

From the different sectors that invest in the human capital, we find that the firms in the service sectors in the top of these firms because all their image depends the service given from the employee to the customer. If the service is good, the customer will be satisfied, if the service is bad, the customer will be unsatisfied, the matter that will distort the image of the firm. These for, it is necessary for the firm to invest in the human capital to keep its image, and to survive for long period.

There are six steps in the human capital function in tourism development as it shown in the figure below:

Figure 1: Human capital function in tourism development

Source: (Basse Benjamin Esu 2012, 282)

As it presented in the figure above, the first step characterized in the formulation of human capital objectives want to achieved. Second, it must identify the tourism discipline attributes. In the third step we find the necessity of developing the human capital strategies such as activities or tools. After, designing the learning tourism curriculum. To know that the human capital has its effect in the tourism sector, the most useful tool is to measure the outcomes. There for, the first is measuring the outcomes of human capital management. After measuring the outcomes, it is necessary to measure the tourism impact on the economy.

According to the reports and statistics of (WTTC 2016a), the continued growth of Travel & Tourism around the world depends on the right people with the right skills being available to meet this demand for additional human capital.

The human capital qualification is a key factor in the customer satisfaction following the important role of the human capital in the hotel (reception, services, ...etc.) (Úbeda-García et al. 2014, 100)

Starting from the importance of the training on performance, According to (Dhar 2015, 422; Dong Kyoon Yoo and Jeong Ah Park 2007) the training helps to increase the employee performance.

Following the study of (Dhar 2015) , there is a strong relationship between the employees training and the quality of services offered by employees in tourist hotels because it improve the employees performance.

In addition, (Úbeda-García et al. 2014) found that the implementation of training policies improve the business results in the hotels.

Inside the tourism sector, we find that the quality of restauration services or the food service from the important services that enhance the image of the tourism in the country. According to (Ravichandran et al. 2015, 158; Eaglen, Lashley, and Thomas 2000),”the training could be considered as a competitive strategic advantage for restaurant to use to increase customer and employee satisfaction while also improving the productivity of the employees”.

The clear results of the positive effect of training on tourism is seen in Dubai. The training solutions is the external training arm of the department of tourism and commerce Marketing (DTCM). Training Solutions is different from other training delivered by colleges, universities and other training institutions because it takes the best tools and learning of the tourism and hospitality sectors and ensures relevance to the marketplace at every stage.

In association with the American Hotels and Lodging Association (AHLA), DTCM Training Solutions provides a wide range of hospitality related training programs, some of these programs include:

- AHLA START Program for UAE national job-seekers interested to join the hospitality industry,
- AHLA Front line hotel staff training,
- AHLA E-learning hospitality training portal,

- AHLA Hospitality supervisory and management modules,
- AHLA Hospitality train-the-trainer programs.

In association with the National HR Development and Employment Authority (also known as TANMIA), the DTCM's Emiratization Task Force for Tourism (ETFT) launched the job-linked MAHARAT training program to encourage Emirati job-seekers to join the fast-expanding hotel industry.

To promote the tourism in the countries, there are different methods follows. Because the first important cycle in tourism is the human capital. So, it is necessary to invest in the human capital for tourism. From the important ways of investing in human capital is training, where following different studies, the training covers global trend in sustainable tourism. The sustainable tourism training offers different benefits for the employees or employers in the tourism industry:

- The ability to make informed decisions on how to implement sustainable practices for the company or destination;
- The ability to build and establish viable and actionable sustainable tourism policies and practices for the organization;
- Demonstrate the knowledge by receiving an endorsed certificate.

From the sectors related with the tourism and attract more individuals are restauration sector and hospitality sector due their importance. There for, the training has also its importance in these two sectors as follows:

Training and hospitality:

From the most related sector to the tourism is the hospitality. In this point and The Training can be defined as” the process that provides new and currently employed staff with the short and longer-term knowledge and skills required to perform successfully on the job”(Hayes and Ninemeier 2009, 172)

Training and restauration:

The training could be considered following the study of (Eaglen, Lashley, and Thomas 2000) as a competitive strategic advantage used to increase customer and employees satisfaction while also improving the productivity of the employees.

Tourism in some selected countries:

Following the previous parts, the tourism appears from the important factors of the economic growth. The figure below contains the number of international inbound tourists in some selected countries to understand the importance of some factors rather than others, in addition to the policies followed to get these places.

Figure 2: Number of international inbound tourists in some selected countries, 2000–2013

Source: (Roberto Crotti and Tiffany Misrahi 2015, 54)

In the figure above, there are all of Malaysia, Ukraine, Thailand, Egypt and Syria. From the first view, both of Syria and Egypt even if there are many touristic places in these two countries in addition to the big investments in tourism sector. However, there were in the latest place respectively because of the instability politic in addition to the terrorism and not security in Syria. Egypt also see a deterioration following the political instability in it, the matter that it touches the security. For the other countries, we find that all of Malaysia, Thailand and Ukraine are in the same way even if they see some crisis such as political crisis of Ukraine in 2008. After this crisis, the tourism declined through the instability just for a while due to the policies taken for tourism because it is the important sector in the growth of Ukraine economy. For the two other countries that are Thailand and Malaysia, the governments of the both countries give the tourism its essential part for the investments following the results seen in the countries invested in the tourism from the first side. In the second side, both of Thailand and Malaysia have their own characteristics in living the matter that it enhances the individuals to visit them, in addition the technological appearance in the latest decades. There for, it enhances the professionals to invest in this area. Therefore, the tourism seen the growth as it presented in the figure.

The reality of tourism in Algeria:

Algeria from the few countries that they have many characteristics to be a successful destination of tourism. However, the dark situation under the French colonialism for more than 130 years push it to a worst situation. In addition, the ten-dark decade under terrorism push Algeria into the worst situation in the world through political instability and the absence of the security. This latest period creates a bad image for Algeria, this latest is the answer of the inexistence of tourism in Algeria. However, through the different studies about the important role of tourism in the economic growth, the Algeria government started to give some interest in this sector by expenditures as it seen in the figure below:

Figure 3: Algeria International tourism, expenditures (current US\$) 1995-2013

Source: edited by the authors following data from WDI databases

In the dark decade, there were few expenditures in this sector according to political instability. After the year 2000, the Algerian government start to give more interest to the tourism by expending more. Through the data of gathered from WDI databases, we find that there is a growth in the expenditures in the tourism sector in Algeria through the equation

$y = 3E + 07x - 6E + 10$ with the coefficient determinant R squared equal to 0.7329. Due to the expenditures in the tourism, the number of arrivals respond to the growth in the expenditure as it presented in the figure below:

Figure 4: Algeria International tourism, number of arrivals 1995-2012

Source: edited by the authors following data from WDI databases

During the dark decade, the number of the arrivals were between 520000 visitors in 1995 and 749000 visitors in 1999. After the political stability and the expenditures in the tourism sector, and the appearance the opportunities of investment in different sectors such a service, tourism itself, hydrocarbons, industry and agriculture ...etc., the number of visitors grow rapidly from 866000 in 2000 to 2634000 in 2012. This multiplication in the number of the visitors with 3 times due to the efforts in the tourism sector from a side, in addition to the different touristic places appeared in the whole country. This latest is rich with different natures due to the big surface of Algeria (2381740.2 km²), this surface is full of the touristic places that attract tourist to visit Algeria.

Following the expenditures for tourism, and the growth of the visitors to Algeria. From the important results is the growth in the receipts of tourism in Algeria as a feedback of the expenditures and the arrivals. There for, the figure below demonstrates the tourism receipts for Algeria through tourism in dollar:

Figure 5: International tourism, receipts for Algeria (current US\$) 1995-2013

Source: edited by the authors following data from WDI databases

In the dark decade, the tourism receipts are so small (between 32 million dollars in 1995 and 178 million dollars in 2004 respectively). Following the knowledge spillover, the world about the Algerian states, the touristic places in Algeria in addition to the appearance of the political stability, there was a great receipt in 2005 with 477 million dollars. After this year, the receipts start in fluctuating following the deterioration in the other sectors related with tourism. This receipt could see also as contribution in the GDP of the country as it shown in the table below:

Table1: the contribution of the tourism and travel in the GDP

year	contribution to GDP (bn \$)	contribution to employment (,000)	year	contribution to GDP (bn \$)	contribution to employment (,000)
2000	7	325	2008	12	566
2001	8	382	2009	14	669
2002	9	425	2010	14	660
2003	11	449	2011	14	702
2004	12	572	2012	14	747
2005	12	572	2013	14	747
2006	13	661	2014	15	778
2007	13	594			

Source : <http://wttc-infographic.org/algeria>

Following the table above and (WTTC 2016b), Travel & Tourism generated 327,500 jobs directly in 2015 (3.0% of total employment) and this is forecast to grow by 4.8% in 2016 to 343,000 (3.0% of total employment). This includes employment by hotels, travel agents, airlines and other passenger transportation services (excluding commuter services). It also includes, for example, the activities of the restaurant and leisure industries directly supported by tourists. As long run previsions such as by 2026, Travel & Tourism will account for 475,000 jobs directly, an increase of 3.3% pa over the next ten years. The figure below shows the graph of the data about the contribution of tourism and travel in creating employment in Algeria from 2000 to 2014.

Figure6 : the contribution of tourism and travel in creating employment in Algeria from 2000-2014(thousand)

Source : <http://wttc-infographic.org/algeria>

The effect of tourism in the economic growth seen as rate of GDP. in addition to the table above that it contains the contribution of tourism in creating employment the contribution of tourism in the GDP of the country, the figure below demonstrates the contribution of tourism in the GDP in Algeria:

Figure7 :the contribution of travel and tourism in GDP (billion \$)

Source : <http://wttc-infographic.org/algeria>

The direct contribution of Travel & Tourism to GDP in 2015 was DZD590.0bn (3.5% of GDP). This is forecast to rise by 4.0% to DZD613.9bn in 2016. This primarily reflects the economic activity generated by industries such as hotels, travel agents, airlines and other passenger transportation services (excluding commuter services). But it also includes, for example, the activities of the restaurant and leisure industries directly supported. The direct contribution of Travel & Tourism to GDP is expected to grow by 3.6% pa to DZD873.7bn (3.7% of GDP) by 2026 (WTTC 2016b)

Incentives to grow up with the tourism sector:

From the most important key factors to enhance the tourism in a country is the transport. But, following (Roberto Crotti and Tiffany Misrahi 2015, 42), the Algeria ranking in 113 place in the field of air transport infrastructure. This latest shows that the Algerian government neglect this important field. For that, we see that the result of this negligence touches the tourism at first following the big relationship between the air-transport infrastructure and tourism.

Latest path to boost the tourism in Algeria:

In the study of G20 presented in the report (UNWTO and WTTC 2012), revealed that visa facilitation has historically increased international tourist arrivals of affected markets by 5-25% following the implementation of policy changes. The actual gain depends largely on the specific visa facilitation actions taken and the markets affected. In addition, the results in the report

(UNWTO and WTTC 2013) show that facilitating visas for tourists could create as many as 2.6 million additional jobs in the APEC economies by 2016 and an additional US\$ 89 billion in international tourism receipts generated by 57 million more tourists visiting APEC destinations. Also, according to the report (UNWTO and WTTC 2014), ASEAN stands to gain between 6 to 10 million additional international tourist arrivals by 2016 from improved visa facilitation.

There for and according to (Oxford Business Group 2016), the Algerian authorities have recently announced plans to overhaul visa requirements with an eye to boosting visitor numbers, part of a broader push to stimulate growth in the tourism sector and diversify the economy.

From the most difficult procedure in the first to get a visa to travel in Algeria is the document, the foreign visitors must apply for a visa in advance from the Algerian diplomatic mission abroad, and provide a number of documents in support of their application. Where for example, the necessity of an official invitation from a local company for business travelers. According to (Roberto Crotti and Tiffany Misrahi 2015, 7), “the visas is from the major obstacle to attract foreign tourists to the country”.

Conclusion and recommendation:

The training of Human capital is critical in the development of any tourist destination. The ability of the destination to develop a competitive edge is a function of the level and quality of human capital base. Algeria is an emerging tourism market. It is richly endowed with cultural and natural resources. However, these resources are waiting for the right human element that will combine expertise and material optimally to produce the expected tourism benefits. Some of the important recommendations to invest in the human capital for tourism industry:

- In the micro level, the necessity of the human resource manager to take responsibility to set the human capital objectives in the firm or society to pursue the corporate vision. In addition, monitor the human capital development process that will facilitate the determination of the tourism discipline attributes to enhance the achievement of the targeted human capital objectives, without forgetting the existence of a tourism commitment is so important to derive the tourism process through an adequate budgetary appropriation.

- In the macroeconomic level, the existence of the training programs will be so important as the most effective human capital strategy that it push the stakeholders to generate tourism curriculum developed with certificate, diploma and degree levels.

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